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D8.3 Report on developments of tools for mapping integrated pressures, exposure, and risk in T8.4

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Preface

This document is the deliverable D8.3 of the Task 8.4 of NECCTON. Its objective is to outline methods and results of multiple environmental pressures mapping and vulnerability of marine ecosystems and target species.

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1. Executive Summary

We developed tools for mapping integrated pressures, exposure, and risk, with a focus on four new climate change (CC) indices: Aerobic Growth Index, Aragonite Saturation index, Hypoxia index, and Heat Wave Hazard index. We also demonstrate some results from the Plastic, Mercury, Persistent Organic Pollutants and oil spill hazard indices. We calculated the CC indices then validated them in a small subset of sample data from existing models in the Northwest European Shelf. We then combined the indices into a multi-stressor index. We developed the evaluation framework to test the tool functionality. In this report, we present the software tools, the methodology to calculate the indices, and the evaluation framework.

2. Scope

In this report, we describe the tools to address multiple pressures maps and habitat responses, which were developed in Task 8.4 of NECCTON, led by PML, in the framework of the work package 8 of the project. The software tools were tested in the Northwest Shelf (NWS) and evaluated for transfer to the other Monitoring and Forecasting Centers of the Copernicus Marine Service.

Multiple stressor metrics were derived from the simulations of the models developed in NECCTON (see the Definitions in Deliverable 8.1):

1. **The Climate change stressor index** (which is the product 24 in the NECCTON list of products). This is a unified climate-multi-stressor indicators, which consist of different sub-products relative to ocean warming, deoxygenation, acidification and changes in primary productivity (led by PML)
2. **The multi-stressor index** (which is the product 25 in the NECCTON list of products). This is multiple stressor metrics integrating climate, pollutant, and fishery pressures (all WP8 partners contributing to the development).

The documented software to compute the metrics was shared in Milestone 8.2 and the underpinning research and innovation is reported in the present D8.3. In particular, this deliverable, describes the tools to generate the above products 24 and 25. This deliverable does not describe the actual products 24 and 25. These were defined in Deliverable 8.1, and will be computed and reported in 2026.

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3. Acronyms and Definitions

AGI	Aerobic Growth Index	One of the Climate change Indices
AMM7	Atlantic Meridional Margins 7km.	The name of the Grid name covering the Northwest Shelf
BGC	Biogeochemistry	How chemical elements flow through living organisms and their physical environment.
BS	Baltic Sea	Model Domain for the Baltic
CC	Climate Change	Anthropogenic impact on the environment
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service.	CMEMS is a provider of physical, biogeochemical and sea ice reference data on the marine environment.
ERSEM	European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model	A Marine Biogeochemistry model.
FABM	Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models	Software for coupling BGC and physical circulation models
Hg	Mercury	Chemical symbol for Mercury
HTL	Higher Trophic Levels	Typically means zooplankton, fish and other higher trophic levels.
HWHI	Heat Wave Hazard Index.	See below
MeHg	Methylmercury	Extremely toxic organometallic mercury compound
MSI	Multi-Stressor Index	See Below
NECCON	New Copernicus Capability for Trophic Ocean Networks	This project
NEMO	Nucleus or European Modelling of the Ocean	Ocean circulation model
NWS	Northwest Shelf	A NEMO Domain, also known as AMM7.
PCB	Polychlorinated biphenyl	Organochlorine compounds, a class of known POPs.
POPs	Persistent Organic Pollutants	Class of toxic chemical pollutants
WW	Wet Weight	Total weight of a sample, including the weight of the water it contains.
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language	A human readable nested dictionary file format.

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4. Introduction

Marine ecosystems are increasingly exposed to anthropogenic environmental changes that may cause stress to the organisms (Hajji & Lucas, 2024). Several of the sources of stress are directly linked to carbon dioxide emissions from combustion of fossil fuels and land use change (Brierley & Kingsford, 2009). The anthropogenic CO₂ can be directly absorbed by the ocean into carbonic acid, which leads to an acidification of the marine environment (Doney et al., 2025). As a greenhouse gas, anthropogenic CO₂ causes the atmosphere to hold onto more heat, warming the earth system. Approximately 90% of the additional heat is absorbed by the ocean, and this has significant impacts to the water temperature, oxygen concentration, and circulation patterns (Kwiatkowski et al., 2020; World Meteorological Organization, 2025). In addition, the criticality of global and local pollution from emerging and persistent contaminants, along with the impact of fisheries, further alters the functional responses of marine organisms affecting their growth, reproduction, and overall health (Arnot & Gobas, 2004; Authority, 2012; Beusen et al., 2022; Hajji & Lucas, 2024; Pitcher et al., 2017).

The goal of the NECCTON project is to enable the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) to deliver novel products that inform marine biodiversity conservation and food resources management, by merging new data into innovative ecosystem models that integrate biological and abiotic components, habitats, and stressors of marine ecosystems.

In this document, we focus on some of the “Stressor” products of NECCTON, and in particular on the methodology used to combine them to derive multi-stressor products.

The Climate change stressor index (product 24 in Deliverable 8.1) includes four climate change stressor indices as sub-products, namely the Aerobic Growth Index (AGI), Heat Wave Hazard Index (HWHI), the Aragonite Saturation index, and the Hypoxia index.

The multi-stressor index is then computed by integrating the climate change stressors with additional sources of marine stress, which were introduced in the NECCTON Deliverable D8.2, and include plastic, mercury, oil spills, fishing pressure index, and Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs). We built the methodological framework to include all the above stressors in in the combined stressors. In this report, we show also the results of the practical computation and mapping of this multi-stressor index in the North West Shelf. But in this case the multi-stressor index includes only the integrated climate change stressors, because data for the other stressors were not available in the study region.

The seven marine life species that are target of these stressors were identified in the first NECCTON stakeholder workshop. The stakeholders were given the following instructions to lead their decision making in the NECCTON stakeholder workshop (quote from the stakeholder session):

“We are preparing a tool to produce habitat suitability indexes for target marine species that take into account multiple environmental stressors, e.g. mean temperature, heat waves, low oxygen levels, acidification. This will offer information on current species habitat suitability and potentially also for future distribution, in relation to climate change. The tool will be potentially of general scope, so applicable for any user-defined species, provided the necessary input data (e.g. temperature ranges, critical oxygen thresholds, etc.). We will be testing the tool on a selection of target species from the

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North East Atlantic / North Western European Continental Shelf and we would like to ask you to suggest some species for this, in order to produce some relevant results.

1. can you suggest some commercially relevant (either for fisheries or otherwise) target species you are especially interested in?
2. can you suggest some relevant species, not necessarily directly exploited, but important from an ecological perspective (e.g. habitat forming seagrass, charismatic species like cold water corals, etc.)
3. from the above, can you provide suggestions for both pelagic and benthic species. “

The initial set of species selected based on the responses of the stakeholders, was refined by removing: (1) the species that would be impractical to include due to requiring ad-hoc methods (e.g. Natura 2000 sites, some shellfish) or (2) were too complex to treat (e.g. European eel) in the framework of this project.

Seven fish and other species were selected as a result. The four target fish species were *Clupea harengus* (Atlantic herring), *Gadus morhua* (Atlantic Cod), *Dicentrarchus labrax* (European Seabass) and *Sparus aurata* (Seabream). In addition to the fish species, *Mytilus edulis* (Blue Mussel), Seaweeds and Cold-Water Corals were included. The seaweed group was created combining several important seaweed species which can all be found in the Northwest European Shelf seas: *Chondrus crispus*, *Fucus spiralis*, *Laminaria digitata*, *Laminaria saccharina*, *Palmaria palmata*, and *Pelvitia canaliculata*.

We note here that the sensitivity to stressors is expected to be species-specific. This means that in most cases, each species will be impacted differently by each of the sources of stress, and we may not use a single stressor for all species. We also use the term “species” loosely, as “Cold Water Coral”, “Seaweeds” are not species at all but rather groups of physiologically similar species.

In the preliminary methods description, we focus on the coupled physical-biogeochemical model NEMO-ERSEM model employed in the Northwest European Shelf (NWS) seas, using a specific model domain, namely the Atlantic Meridional Margins (AMM) domain. However, these indices has the potential to be computed over the other Monitoring and Forecasting Centers (MFCs) of the Copernicus Marine Service covered by the model simulations of NECCTON. Software tools will be tested in the NWS and evaluated for transfer to other MFCs.

Structure of the Document

The document is structured such that, following this brief introduction, we outline each of the stressor indices, the software used to generate them, and we propose a method to combine them into a multi-stressor index. The results section included tables showing the parameters of the fits for HWHI and AGI, then a comparison of changes for each species.

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5. Procedures

Description of software tools.

We follow the technical specification of the pollutants and stressors products in D8.1 (Canu, 2023). This document thoroughly describes the co-products, sub-variables, and all the technical product nomenclature (netcdf variable name, standard name, long name, short name, units) and we have followed this protocol in the current document.

To generate the four climate change stressors, we use example model data. These data were obtained from existing simulations that use a branch of the ERSEM BGC model, that is the NECCTON ERSEM branch. The simulation name is AMM7-RECICLE-BGC-IPSL-CM5A-MR, from the Resolving Climate Impacts on shelf and Coastal Sea Ecosystems (ReCICLE) project simulations¹. The overall aim of this project was to identify and quantify the potential future response to climate change of the simple plant life (phytoplankton) forming the base of the food chain of the shelf sea ecosystems and to assess the likely range of this response using a state of the art coupled hydrodynamic-ecosystem model at an exceptionally fine resolution. As such, ReCICLE model simulations are an excellent starting point for testing the climate change stressors. The NECCTON models simulations and computation of the marine pollution and stressor products are planned to be validated and released by month 36 of the project (MS8.3). The ReCICLE simulation, as the NECCTON one, is a NEMO-ERSEM simulation, coupled using FABM, in the AMM7 domain. The climate forcing is taken from the CMIP5 simulation IPSL-CM5A-MR in the RCP-8.5 scenario. Simulated marine data exists for this model between 1990 and 2100. The climate change stressor indices and multi-stressor software tools are publicly available on github in the PMLmodelling group².

The installation and execution of the code is described in the `README.md` file, which is in the base directory of the repository. This code is python3 based and uses a conda environment to install and maintain its dependencies. The analysis set up is described in a human-readable yaml file, some of which will need to be set up for each input simulation. This code is designed to take existing NEMO-ERSEM model simulations, calculate each of the indices, and output them into netcdf4 files using the NECCTON file format. The output file metadata is taken from D8.1, table 3.6.6 and 3.7.6. The overall structure of the code is set up such that a central generalised indexing tool handles the input and output, while individual index calculations are performed by specialised functions in separate directories.

The Aerobic Growth and Heat Wave Hazard indices both require habitat distribution data to parameterize the sensitivities of each species to the index. Table 1 shows the source of data for each species' habitat.

¹ ReCICLE project: <https://pml.ac.uk/projects/recicle-resolving-climate-impacts-on-shelf-and-coa/>

² Link to GitHub page: https://github.com/pmlmodelling/neccton_cc_indices

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Table 1: The habitat depth range and data source for each species.

Species	Habitable Depth Range	Habitat Data source
<i>Clupea harengus</i> (Atlantic herring)	0 - 364 m	https://www.fishbase.se/summary/Clupea-harengus.html
<i>Gadus morhua</i> (Atlantic Cod)	0 - 600 m	https://www.fishbase.se/summary/Gadus-morhua.html
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i> (European seabass)	0 - 100 m	https://www.fishbase.se/summary/Dicentrarchus-labrax.html
<i>Sparus aurata</i> (Seabream)	0 - 150 m	https://www.fishbase.se/summary/Sparus-aurata.html
<i>Mytilus edulis</i> (Blue mussel)	0 - 41 m	https://www.sealifebase.se/summary/Mytilus-edulis.html https://obis.org/taxon/140480
Seaweeds	0 – 42 m	https://www.britannica.com/science/seaweed https://obis.org (multiple links)
Cold water Coral	82 - 3000 m	https://obis.org/occurrence/003c04ad-46c4-44e9-a418-cadb0ea63dd5

Climate Change Indices

Aerobic Growth Index

The Aerobic Growth Index (AGI) combines the simultaneous stress of increasing sea temperatures and deoxygenation in a single, species-specific index (Clarke et al., 2021, Morée et al., 2023). AGI represents the minimal theoretical combination of oxygen and temperature that allows a species to meet its bare metabolic demands (i.e. just surviving).

The AGI is calculated as:

$$AGI_i = \frac{pO_2^s}{pO_2^d} = \frac{pO_2^s}{pO_{2,i}^{threshold} \cdot \left(\frac{W_i}{W_{inf}}\right)^{1-d} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{j_2 - j_i}{T_i^{pref}} - \frac{j_2 - j_i}{T_i}\right)}$$

Where the parameters are:

- pO_2 threshold is the volume-weighted 10th percentile of all in-habitat pO_2 values.
- T_{pref} is the volume-weighted 50th percentile of all in-habitat temperature values.
- AGI_{crit} is the volume weighted 10th percentile of all AGI values in a species' habitat.
- W_i / W_{inf} , is the ratio of mean biomass to maximal biomass, but reduces to 1/3.

The critical AGI threshold AGI_{crit} , is the lower aerobic growth limit, above which a species can grow and reproduce. If the ratio AGI / AGI_{crit} is > 1 then the environment is viable. To sustain a viable population for a particular species, additional aerobic scope is needed until AGI is above AGI_{crit} . Habitat volume is lost or unavailable when the annual mean AGI is below AGI_{crit} .

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Using this method, we calculated the AGI input parameters for all seven species based on Temperature, Salinity and Oxygen data from World Ocean Atlas 2023, and habitat data and depth ranges as listed in table 1. The results of this calculation are compared with the Morée et al. (2023) parameterisation in table 2 below. Note that Morée et al. (2023) provides parameter values for 47 fish species but only two of the species of interest in NECCTON, Atlantic Herring (*Clupea harengus*) and Atlantic Cod (*Gadus morhua*), are included there or have even been parameterised for AGI before. The differences between our calculated values and Morée et al. (2023) are small and are likely due to using different time ranges, and input datasets. Morée et al. (2023) calculated these parameters using Environmental data of oxygen concentration, potential temperature, and salinity for the years 1850–2100 from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) multi-model ensemble historical, SSP5-8.5, and SSP1-2.6 and pre-industrial scenarios from the six models: CNRM-ESM2-1, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, UKESM1-0-LL, IPSL-CM6A-LR, GFDL-ESM4, and CanESM5. However, we performed the calculation using two different WOA 2023 input datasets periods: 1971-2000 and 1995-2014, which are observational based data products.

More widely, AGI has only been deployed in two publications and only to fish (Clarke et al., 2021; Morée et al., 2023). It has never been applied to bivalves, corals or seaweeds. As the input datasets needed to calculate AGI parameters for seaweed, cold water corals and blue mussels do exist, it is technically feasible to calculate AGI for these species.

We have used WOA data to inform the temperature, salinity and oxygen ranges. These datasets have a resolution of 1° and global scope, but may struggle to fully represent shallow coastal environments, especially the intertidal range. The global WOA datasets were used to avoid niche truncation (i.e. calculating the parameters using only at the habitat within the model domain).

Table 2: Parameters for the AGI index, showing the parameter for Moree et al 2023, and the version calculated here using the 1971–2000-time range.

Species	<i>Clupea harengus</i> (Atlantic Herring)	<i>Gadus morhua</i> (Atlantic Cod)	<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i> (Seabass)	<i>Sparus aurata</i> (Seabream)	<i>Mytilus edulis</i> (Blue Mussel)	Cold Water Corals	Seaweeds
Temp. Pref., °C (Morée 2023)	6.23	3.77					
Temp Pref., °C 1971-2000	5.00	4.21	12.55	14.61	7.646	4.349	6.583
pO_2 Thresh., atm (Morée 2023)	0.195	0.178					
pO_2 Thresh, atm 1971-2000	0.168	0.164	0.179	0.172	0.176	0.036	0.189
AGI Crit. (Morée 2023)	1.1	1.17					
AGI Crit. 1971-2000	1.026	0.929	1.125	1.19	1.069	0.364	1.047

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Heat Wave Hazard Index

Our literature review found two possible candidates for the heat wave index. The first uses a physical definition of heat wave from Hobday et al. (2016) as a period of at least 5 days with Temperature greater than the 95th percentile of Temperature in that location, T_{95} . However, the Hobday method does not include species-specific responses. Different species may have different thermal tolerance levels. The second heat wave index candidate is the Galli et al. (2017) approach, called the Heat Wave Hazard Index (HWHI). In HWHI, a heat wave is defined in a species-response-oriented way as the species-specific number of days above that species' threshold temperature that result in lethal or sublethal effects for a target species. For this reason, we use the Galli et al. (2017) approach here. For each species, the threshold temperature, T_{thresh} , is calculated as the 95th weighted percentile of the temperature for all locations where that species has been observed to inhabit, where the species-specific weighting is based on their habitat probably. We also define a minimum heatwave duration, which is set five days for all species in this initial testing phase. This method does not consider other factors that determines a species habitat – it simply links to thermal stress.

The heat wave hazard index, HWHI, is the annual cumulative sum of the daily temperature anomaly, $T - T_{\text{thresh}}$, for all periods in that year where the temperature exceeds T_{thresh} for multiple consecutive days longer than the minimum heatwave duration. The HWHI is in units of degree*days, as it is the temperature above the threshold multiplied by the duration of the heat wave in days. In effect it's the integral along the time direction of the warming above the species-specific threshold.

We define a critical value for HWHI of 100 degree*days, for all species. In effect, this value of 100 means that there has been approximately 33 days in a year that were 3 degrees above the species temperature threshold, or 100 days that were one degree more than T_{thresh} , or some other combination of days and warming. Each species has a temperature threshold which is based on the 95th percentile of their observed habitat, so it's acceptable to use the same HWHI threshold for all species. This value of 100 was chosen arbitrarily and may need to be further tuned in further extensions and may be further tuned to be species-specific.

Similarly to the AGGI, we used global WOA data to inform the temperature ranges. These datasets have a resolution of 1° and global scope. The global WOA datasets were used to avoid niche truncation (i.e. calculating the parameters using only at the habitat within the model domain) but may struggle to fully represent shallow coastal environments, especially the intertidal range. For this reason, the seaweeds have a potentially unrealistically low temperature threshold.

Table 32: HWHI parameters.

Species	<i>Clupea harengus</i> (Atlantic herring)	<i>Gadus morhua</i> (Atlantic Cod)	<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i> (European seabass)	<i>Sparus aurata</i> (Seabream)	<i>Mytilus edulis</i> (Blue mussel)	Seaweeds	Cold water Coral
Temp. threshold, °C	17.1	15.4	25.5	25.7	18.5	13.3	18.3
Duration, days	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

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HWHI threshold	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
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Hypoxia

A sufficient supply of dissolved oxygen is essential to most marine organisms, but oxygen concentration can sometimes fall below the basic living requirement for some species. Hypoxia occurs when oxygen concentration falls below ~ 6 mg/l ($180 \text{ } \mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$), and anoxia occurs when oxygen concentration falls below ~ 2 mg/l ($60 \text{ } \mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$). Other threshold values exist in literature, but here we use the thresholds for the North Sea from Devlin et al. (2023).

Using a similar method to the HWHI, we set the hypoxia index as the annual cumulative sum of the daily oxygen concentration anomaly, $O_{\text{thresh}} - O$, for all periods in that year where the Oxygen concentration, O , is below the Oxygen Concentration threshold, O_{thresh} , for multiple consecutive days longer than the minimum hypoxia duration.

We initially defined a hypoxic region as $<80 \text{ mmol m}^{-3}$ and 5 days (though this limit is closer to the threshold for anoxia than hypoxia). However, using this criterion led to zero hypoxic events in the Northwest European Shelf domain in our simulations, even at the end of the 21st century in the enhanced fossil fuel scenario, RCP8.5. As such, we choose to loosen these criteria to three consecutive days below ~ 6 mg/l or 180 mmol m^{-3} , but even this loose thresholds did not significantly increase the number or size of hypoxic events in the NWS. Hypoxic events may occur in this region, but typically on scales that cannot be represented in the NWS AMM7 grid (M. Devlin et al., 2023; Huthnance et al., 2022; Queste et al., 2013; Schmidt & Diallo, 2024).

These thresholds and durations are species independent, and as such there is only one hypoxia index in this suite. However, each species may have a different sensitivity to hypoxia, so the Hypoxia index's contribution to multi-stressor index is weighted according to species habitat and sensitivity, as described below.

Table 4: 3 Hypoxia parameters

	Hypoxia Threshold, mmol m^{-3}	Duration Threshold, days
All species	180	3

Aragonite saturation

Aragonite saturation state is a measure of how easily aragonite, a form of calcium carbonate, dissolves in seawater. Aragonite saturation is a key indicator of ocean acidification and the health of marine ecosystems. As carbonate ion concentration declines, certain species, particularly those that form hard structures as juveniles, may become stressed. A decrease in Aragonite saturation indicates that it is harder for organisms to build and maintain their skeletons and shells. In particular, species that form hard structures such as corals and other calcifiers need an Aragonite saturation greater than 3.0 to grow optimally, especially in their juvenile state (Xu et al., 2023; Yamamoto-Kawai et al., 2011).

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When Aragonite Saturation falls below 1, these species can become highly stressed (Hoegh-Guldberg et al., n.d.; Matear & Lenton, 2018).

The aragonite saturation is calculated directly in the model ERSEM and is based on Zeebe & Wolf-Gladrow (2001) that follows Mucci (1983) with pressure corrections from Millero (1995). It requires as inputs Temperature, Salinity, Pressure and Carbonate ion concentration. The code that performs this calculation is available in the ERSEM online codebase: (Marine Systems Modelling group, 2022). The specific carbonate calculation is in the src directory in the carbonate.F90 file³. To convert the model output to a NECCTON-ready index, we take the annual mean of the monthly values. The surface ocean is not projected to become undersaturated, so this is mostly relevant for cold water corals.

Table 5: 4 Aragonite Saturation parameters

	Stress	High Stress
All species	< 3	<1

Similarly the Hypoxia index, the aragonite saturation index is species independent. Each species may have a difference sensitivity to aragonite saturation, so the aragonite saturation index's contribution to multi-stressor index is weighted according to species habitat and sensitivity.

Pollutant indices

The NECCTON models to simulate Plastic, Mercury, oil spills and POPs described in D8.1 and D8.2 are used here to estimate impacts on the HTLs. Risk analysis is performed for each stressor, and we developed a method that can include them in a multi-stressor index, using the approach described below. In this report, we show also the results of the practical computation and mapping of this multi-stressor index in the North-West Shelf. But in this case, the multi-stressor index includes only the integrated climate change stressors, because data for the other stressors were not available in the study region.

Assessing oil spill hazards in probabilistic terms as a single pressure index

In the context of natural hazards, the risk for a set of territorial elements is defined as a function of hazard, value, and vulnerability (UNESCO, 1972). Hazard refers to the likelihood that any particular area will be affected by a destructive event within a given period, value refers to the numbers and types of elements exposed to the destructive hazard, and vulnerability is a measure of the capability of the exposed elements to counteract the destructive effects of the event and thus refers to the proportion of value at stake for a given event.

Oil spills present hazards that vary dynamically in magnitude based on external parameters like sea currents, waves, wind, and sea temperatures, which change in space and time. In distinguishing accidental from operational oil spills, two types of hazard indices can be defined. The former pertains to medium (7–700 tons) and large (>700 tons) spills according to the International Tanker Owners Pollution Federation Limited (ITOPF) classification. The latter refers to operational discharges (<7 tons), including bilge water from machinery spaces, fuel oil sludge, and oily ballast water from fuel

³ Link to current master file: <https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem/blob/master/src/carbonate.F90>

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tanks. In the context of the NECCTON project, we examined accidental oil spills due to their well-documented impact on the ecosystem. To this end, we created a virtual spill scenario based on the historical wreck of the MT Haven, (HAVEN), oil spill (off the Port of Genoa, 1991), which is recognized as the largest shipwreck in European waters and one of the worst oil pollution cases in the Mediterranean.

A simplified HAVEN oil spill scenario was designed to represent the continuous 50-hour release of heavy Iranian crude oil (API5 = 31) at a spill rate of 200 tons/hour, resulting in a total spilled oil volume of 10,000 tons. The simulation duration was set at 25 days (600 hours). More than two million virtual spills were sampled across the entire Mediterranean using the latest SAR-derived detection inventory (Figure 1).

Figure 1 An example of 10,000 sources of virtual spills (Dong et al., 2022). Six concentration areas outlined in red are associated with (1) the Gibraltar Strait, (2) the extended Port of Algiers, (3) the north Ligurian Sea sector, (4) the bunkering areas of Malta, (5) the Otranto Strait, and (6) the extended Port Said. The cumulative total is 10,000 tons of oil spilled over 2018-2021.

In the results, a sample composed of i virtual spills, $i = 1, \dots, N$ constitutes the hourly oil concentration fields $C_i^j(x, y)$ at the sea surface and coastlines, where x and y are the longitude and latitude of the bin respectively, $j = 1, \dots, 600$ is time in hours. Each concentration field is quantized using a simple dimensionless step-function $H(C_i^j(x, y))$ defined for each spill i at the sea surface and coastline:

$$H\left(\max_j C_i^j(x, y)\right) = \begin{cases} 1, & \max_j C_i^j(x, y) > THR \\ 0, & \max_j C_i^j(x, y) \leq THR, \end{cases}$$

where $THR = 0.1 \text{ ton/km}^2$ denotes the threshold sea surface concentration and 0.01 ton/km on the coastline, i.e., the values that, if exceeded, could lead to destructive events.

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The values of the concentration thresholds in hazard mapping are critical since they control the loss of the oil concentration PDF tails. Moreover, because there are no strict conventional criteria for selecting them, the resulting uncertainty hinders the comparability of hazard maps computed by different research groups. Although much progress was made by French-McCay (2016), the definition of thresholds is still under discussion and needs further research. Currently, three types of thresholds are distinguished: biological, socioeconomic, and those linked to response efficiency (Table 5).

The biological thresholds are typically species-specific, and measuring the population response values is challenging. In case of the HAVEN oil spill, the post-accident environmental assessment indicated substantial injury to subtidal *Posidonia/Cymodocea* (seagrass) beds, the deep-sea benthic community, and associated commercial fisheries (Martinelli et al., 1995). Although the International Tanker Owners Pollution Federation Limited (ITOPF, 2014b) expected recovery within one to three years, a restoration program initiated 12 years later revealed the tar residuals on the seabed and the oil products still contained in the wreck (Amato, 2003). So, the biological thresholds were surpassed both in the short term and long term.

The values we used represent the socioeconomic thresholds linked to mariculture, fishing, ports, water supply intakes, coastal-dependent businesses, tourism, and aesthetics. Importantly, these values were close to the 10% percentile of the oil concentration PDFs. Such a formal criterion can be applied in the absence of a priori information about the thresholds.

Table 6: Sea surface and coastline oil concentration thresholds used to define the level of concern in stochastic oil spill modelling.

Domain (reference)	Source of oil	Amount of oil per spill	Thresholds	
			At the sea surface	On the coastline
Mexico Gulf (Barker, 2011)	Deepwater Horizon blowout	~470,000 m ³	Dull sheen thickness of ~1 μm	Tarball density of ~2 m ⁻²
South Adriatic and North Ionian seas (Liubartseva et al., 2015)	Operational spills along shipping lanes	0.02–0.5 m ³	0.001 gm ⁻²	0.1 gm ⁻¹
Mississippi River (Horn and French McCay, 2016)	Crude-by-rail releases	~100–3000 m ³	1 gm ⁻² , 10 gm ⁻²	N/A
Adriatic Sea (Liubartseva et al., 2016)	Accidental spills from oil platforms	9600 tons	1 gm ⁻²	100 gm ⁻¹
Algarve area, Portugal (Sepp-Neves et al., 2016)	Accidental and operational spills	10,000–50,000 tons and 1–46 tons	N/A	1 gm ⁻²
Alaskan Beaufort and Chukchi Seas (French McCay et al., 2017)	Accidental blowout and pipeline leaks	Blowout: 119,240 m ³ , Pipeline leaks: ~100–5000 m ³	Socioeconomic: 0.1–1 gm ⁻² , Biota impact: 10 gm ⁻²	100 gm ⁻²
Canadian waters (Creber et al., 2017)	Ship-source oil spills	43 m ³	Socioeconomic: 0.01 gm ⁻² , Biota impact: 1 gm ⁻² , Response efficiency: 8 gm ⁻²	Socioeconomic: 1 gm ⁻² , Biota impact: 10 gm ⁻²
Taranto Port (present work)	Accidental spill from the single-point buoy mooring and subsea pipeline	600 tons	0.01 gm ⁻²	0.1 gm ⁻¹

The probabilities of oil exceeding the prescribed threshold are represented by the hazard indices $P(x, y)$:

$$P(x, y) = N^{-1} \sum_i^N H(C_i(x, y)).$$

Hazard indices ranged between 0 and 1, where 1 denotes the maximum hazard and 0 indicates no hazard. Considering hazard indices at the sea surface, we used the maximum oil concentrations. For coastal hazards, the maximum oil concentration can be substituted by the 600-hour values as oil accumulates on the coastlines. The hazard indices were computed on one arc-minute grid (~1.5 km

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in the Mediterranean), without compromising computational efficiency and visualization accuracy (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Hazard indices in probability terms at the sea surface (a) and coastlines (b).

The hazard index values were relatively low, rarely reaching 10^{-2} . Such orders of magnitude were expected, as the initial sources of the oil spill were highly distributed across the entire domain. These values align with the OSRA-based probability maps for the Gulf of Mexico (Ji et al., 2021), in which the initial sources were also highly distributed (though homogeneously) across the basin. Generally, unlike highly distributed sources, a point source provides the largest hazard indexes, asymptotically approaching a value of one at the source's location.

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Assessing Risk from Mercury Dietary Intake

Mercury biomagnifies through marine food webs, thus increasing in concentrations along with trophic levels up to very high concentrations in top predators worldwide (Médiéu et al., 2024). Bioconcentration in phytoplankton causes the largest increase in concentrations, which are up to 10^4 times higher in the cell than in water. For each subsequent increase in trophic level, Hg concentrations are estimated to increase around 7 times (Gosnell & Mason, 2015; Hammerschmidt & Fitzgerald, 2006; Harding et al., 2018) and dietary intake is considered the main route of Hg accumulation in the Higher Trophic Levels (HLT) (Schartup et al., 2019). Bioaccumulation of Hg reflects exposure from the diet and environment over the lifetime of the organism and is influenced by several ecological and biogeochemical factors (Cossa et al., 2012). About 90% of the Hg in the tissues of the HLT is methylmercury (MeHg), the most toxic and bioaccumulative mercury species that is microbially produced in the marine environment. The impacts of MeHg on marine wildlife health are not well established, but available information has been summarized previously. Risk from Hg exposure for the HLT can be assessed either based on tissue concentrations or diet intake (Evers et al., 2024). Ecotoxicological studies based on waterborne exposure are considered less suitable to estimate risk of Hg exposure under realistic environmental conditions as they often adopt unrealistically high initial concentrations of Hg and usually do not assess the variations in concentration over time related to Hg degassing and adhesion to the wall, nor the fraction of Hg that is acquired through the diet. One limitation of tissue-residue approaches is the assumption that a toxic effect is not observed unless the chemical reaches the site of action, and the target tissue is in equilibrium with external concentrations. However, it is not clear that these assumptions are entirely appropriate for MeHg, and tissue-residue thresholds do not distinguish between sublethal effects that may have dramatically different, yet highly meaningful ecological consequences (Depew et al., 2012). When mercury is provided as food at a known concentration, already scavenged by food particles, the actual exposure level can be more accurately quantified and sublethal endpoints can be assessed. Recommendations for human health are also based on thresholds of “Tolerable Weekly Intake” (TWI) that depend on the amount of mercury ingested and the person's body weight (MeHg TWI = $1.3 \mu\text{g}$ per kg of bw per week)⁴.

The approach based on diet exposure leverages the NECCTON mercury products to estimate potential impacts on the HLT. Risk of reproductive impairment for planktivorous and predatory fish is estimated from the ratio of the modelled concentration of MeHg in the Lower Trophic Levels (LTL) such as phytoplankton, zooplankton, and forage fish, to ecotoxicological thresholds. The method also integrates information on fish ecology (WP7) to better represent different target species. Due to its societal relevance, an indicator of human risk based on concentrations in forage fish is also presented.

Risk Quotient for fish: modeled MeHg concentrations in different plankton functional types or forage fish (PFTs) are combined with information on diet composition and depth of habitat ($z_{0,j} - z_{1,j}$) to calculate the dietary exposure for a given HLT species j . The risk quotient (RQ) is then calculated by

⁴ EFSA, 2012. Mercury in food – EFSA updates advice on risks for public health. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/press/news/121220> Last access 4th June 2025.

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comparing the estimated dietary exposure with selected ecotoxicological thresholds for a given endpoint.

$$Exp_{HTL}^j = \sum_{PFT} \overline{MeHg_{PFT}^{z0-z1}} \cdot f_{diet,PFT}^j$$

$$RQ_{end}^j = \frac{Exp_{HTL}^j}{Tresh_{end}}$$

A literature review was carried out to define ecologically meaningful ecotoxicological thresholds. Around 20 papers meeting the research criteria were retrieved and analyzed. The information currently available did not allow inter-specific sensitivity in the analysis, although this can be an important factor (Stefansson et al., 2013). Other authors have already defined different thresholds for different endpoints in fish based on NOAEL (no observed adverse effect level) and LOAEL (lowest observed adverse effect level) values integrated from various studies (Depew et al., 2012), and no strictest thresholds have been identified in more recent studies. Based on this synthesis, the strictest threshold for fish exposure to Hg is a concentration in food of 0.04 ug/g wet weight (w.w.). This threshold is linked to reproductive impairments, thus impacting the fitness of the organisms with possible effects at the population level and was selected for the analysis. Higher thresholds were also estimated by Depew et al. (2012): for the following impacts:

- Biochemical effects: 0.06 ug/g w.w.
- Behavioral effects: 0.5 ug/g w.w.
- Impacts on growth: 1.44 ug/g w.w.
- Mortality: 2.8 g/g w.w.

However, these higher concentrations are unlikely to be found in LTL in nature.

Hazard Quotient (HQ) for humans: Estimated daily intake (EDI) for humans is calculated based on modeled Hg and Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) concentrations in forage fish and assuming an average fish uptake of 100 g per day for a person weighing 70 kg. The Hazard Quotient is then calculated as the ratio between the EDI and the tolerable weekly intake (TWI) dose for MeHg:

- TWI = 1.3 µg kg⁻¹ week⁻¹ (Alexander et al., 2012; EFSA, 2012)
- PFAS: TWI = 4.4 ng kg⁻¹ week⁻¹ (EC, 2022).

Based on the developed HTL bioaccumulation model we are able to calculate the HQ for fish used for human consumption in the North Sea and Baltic Sea for Hg (Figure 4) and PFOS (Figure 5). It should be noted that the Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) uptake limit value is for the sum of 24 selected PFAS, while already PFOS accumulation alone can lead to an exceedance of this limit.

$$EDI = \text{concentration } [\mu\text{g g}^{-1}] * \text{uptake } [\text{g day}^{-1}] / \text{weight } [\text{kg}]$$

$$RQ_{EFSA}^{human} = \frac{7 EDI}{TWI_{EFSA}}$$

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MED: Risk from Hg exposure for planktivorous fish (anchovies and pilchards) and marine mammals (fin whales) was estimated on assuming diet composition and feeding habitat given in Table 6. The results based on preliminary outputs of Hg products are shown in Figure 3.

NWS, BS: For the NWS and BS, we calculated the same risk metrics as for the MED. Due to the advanced bioaccumulation module that includes higher trophic levels, we were able to also calculate human hazard quotient (HQ) due to the consumption of fish (Herring and Cod) for methylmercury (Fig. 4) and PFOS (Fig, 5).

Table 7: Information on diet composition and feeding habitat used to estimate Hg exposure risk for HTL from the output of the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model.

Target Species	Diet composition	model PFTs	Feeding Habitat	Source
Anchovy (<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>)	99% copepods 0.28% micro-zooplankton 0.3% large phytoplankton	Z3, Z4, P1	Nearshore in the upper 100 m depth during summer. Offshore between 100 and 200 m depth during winter	WP7
Pilchard (<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>)	100% copepods	Z3	as above	WP7
Fin whale (<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>)	90% euphasiids, 10% carnivorous zooplankton	Z3, Z4	upper 300 m for the whole year	Notarbartolo di Sciara et al., (2023)

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Figure 3: Example map of risk from Hg exposure for the HTL in the MED estimated with mercury NECCTON products.

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Figure 4: Example map of risk from Hg exposure due to sea food exposure for the HTL in the North Sea and Baltic Sea estimated with mercury NECCTON products.

Figure 5: Example map of risk from PFOS exposure due to sea food consumption for the HTL in the North Sea and Baltic Sea estimated with PFAS NECCTON products.

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Assessing risks from Persistent Organic Pollutants

In the marine environment, Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) accumulate in the lipid tissues of organisms, with biomagnification occurring as these compounds move up the food chain. The primary route of exposure is dietary intake, while uptake from water plays a secondary role. These dynamics are strongly influenced by predator-prey interactions, which dictate contaminant transfer from individual organisms to entire ecosystems. Marine food webs consist of diverse species, ranging from microscopic plankton to apex predators such as whales, all linked through complex feeding relationships. Due to its prevalence in industrial Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB) mixtures and widespread detection in marine systems, PCB-153 was selected as a model compound for studying POP behavior in food web models.

Fish accumulates PCB-153 primarily through respiratory absorption across gill membranes, consumption of contaminated prey, and passive diffusion through skin surfaces. These exposure pathways allow the POPs to enter fish tissues and begin accumulating in lipid-rich organs. Once absorbed, PCB-153 undergoes several elimination processes including gill excretion back into the water column, fecal elimination of unassimilated compounds, and minimal metabolic transformation due to the limited enzymatic capacity of fish to break down chlorinated hydrocarbons. The bioaccumulation dynamics can be mathematically represented by the equation (Arnot & Gobas, 2004; Gobas et al., 1993):

$$\frac{dC_f}{dt} = k_1 C_w + k_d \sum (P_i C_{d,i}) - (k_2 + k_e + k_m + k_g) C_f$$

Where:

- C_w is the concentration of chemical in water (ng/L),
- $C_{d,i}$ is the concentration in prey item i (ng/kg),
- C_f is the concentration in fish (ng/kg),
- k_1 is the rate constant for uptake from water via gills (L/kg/day),
- k_d is the rate constant for chemical uptake from food (kg food/kg fish/day),
- P_i is the fraction of the diet consisting of prey item i ,
- k_2 is the rate constant for the elimination via gills to water (d^{-1}),
- k_e is the rate constant for the elimination by fecal ingestion (d^{-1}),
- k_m is the rate constant for metabolic transformation of chemicals (d^{-1}),
- k_g is the rate constant for growth dilution (d^{-1}).

Huang et al. (2020) applied this modeling framework by integrating the CanMETOP with marine food web models to simulate PCB-153 concentrations across 38 ecologically important fish species. Their results revealed significantly elevated contamination levels in fish populations inhabiting European marine ecosystems, reflecting the region's historical industrial PCB usage patterns and the compound's persistence in temperate marine environments. This spatial pattern highlights that food web models can identify regional contamination hotspots and track the long-term fate of POPs in marine ecosystems. There plans outside the scope of the NECCON project to extend this modeling framework to assess emerging contaminants in marine ecosystems, including plastic-related

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chemicals (organophosphate esters and phthalate esters) and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). The model will help evaluate their bioaccumulation potential and ecological risks to marine fish populations.

Figure 4. Modelled PCB-153 concentrations in marine fish ($\text{ng g}^{-1} \text{ww}$) for various categories. a, Total fish, b, anchovies, c, herring-likes, d, cod-likes, e, flatfish, f, salmon, g, tuna & billfish, and h, other fishes (Huang et al., 2020).

Fisheries Pressure

NIOZ built an R package (“Bfiat”; <https://github.com/EMODnet/Bfiat/>) endowed with functionalities to assess and predict the impact of bottom trawling on the benthos and associated ecosystem functions (Deliverable 8.2; Beauchard and Soetaert⁵). The central element of the package consists in

⁵ Beauchard O, Soetaert K. Bottom fishing assessment tool: an R package to model the effects of bottom trawling on the marine. Ecological Applications, under review.

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a modelling procedure that processes the abundances of benthic invertebrates undergoing a specified trawling regime: trawling disturbance frequency as the number of trawling events per year and trawling gear penetration into the sediment. For assessing the impact on a species, the observed abundance (D) is assumed to result from the concomitantly observed trawling regime according to (1) exposure to the gear expressed as burying depth and (2) recoverability between trawling events through the intrinsic rate of natural increase (approximated with the inversed age at sexual maturity). The instantaneous mortality due to gear impact is a function of penetration depth into the sediment and calibrated according to (Hiddink et al., 2017). Through the logistic growth model, the procedure back-calculates the carrying capacity (K) to an untrawled state (equilibrium). Hence, the assessment is simply expressed by D/K , varying between 0 (worst case) and 1 (no impact; “relative benthic status”; (Pitcher et al., 2017). In practice, this is done for an entire species community whereby the sum of the abundances observed for the different species is divided by the sum of the different back-calculated species carrying capacities. Figure 5 displays an application example in the Dutch sector of the North Sea: highest trawling intensities lead to the highest community depletions, with a clearly perceptible habitat effect.

Figure 5: Bfiat model applications to the Dutch sector of the North Sea (a); dots, sampling stations; black, high hydrodynamics habitat; white, low hydrodynamics habitat; see (Beauchard et al., 2022) for more details. Dot size proportional to trawling intensity (min = 0.09; max = 11.82 yr⁻¹). b) Relative benthic status (observed organism density divided by carrying capacity): interpolated total faunal densities as fraction of summed back-calculated carrying capacities.

Multi stressor Index

Each of the stresses describe above can be detrimental to marine organisms, individually. However, when multiple sources of stress occur simultaneously, the stress on the organism is further compounded (Beusen et al., 2022). To assess the compound stress, we normalise individual stressors, then combined into a multi-stressor for each individual species using the methods below.

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The normalisation process to contribute to the MSI is straightforward. We first define a normalised stressor scale between 0 and 1, where 0 is “no stress”, and 1 is “very stressed”. Each of the individual stressors requires its own unique normalisation process to convert its value to this range. We also fix each stressor to a set range between 0 and 1 such that no individual stressor can be negative or greater than 1.

Initially, several methods were postulated to combine the individual normalised stressors, including a simple mean or a simple maximum. However, the combination needed to consider at first order the largest source of stress for each species, then secondly the compound impact of the other stressors. The sum of the maximum stressor and the mean of the stressors was initially considered, but this method would double count the largest source of stress. As such, we propose the new Multi-Stressor Index to be the sum of the maximum normalised stressor at each point and the mean of the other normalised stressors, excluding the maximum.

$$MSI_{i,j} = \max(\text{indices}_{i,j}) + \frac{\Sigma(\text{indices}_{i,j}) - \max(\text{indices}_{i,j})}{N - 1}$$

Where:

- $\text{indices}_{i,j}$ is a list of indices at the coordinates (i, j) ,
- N is the number of indices,
- \max is the maximum function.

This method does not consider non-linear interactions among stressors, which are highly species-specific. In addition, while the theoretical maximum MSI value would be 2 (i.e. when all normalised stressors contribute a value of 1), but we limit the range to 0-1 such that anything above 1 is considered “very stressed”.

Of the four indices described in this document, the AGI and HWHI already have the species-specific vulnerability component incorporated, so their normalisation process is the same for all species. On the other hand, the Hypoxia and Aragonite saturation indices were generated as a single species-independent index, so they need to have some species-specific weighting to be normalised to a range of 0-1. The weighting factor aims to incorporate each species known relationships to stress. For instance, all four fish species included here have a very low sensitive to aragonite saturation, so their aragonite saturation is normalised to have a low contribution to the MSI. An addition layer of complexity is that some of the HWHI and Hypoxia indices increase with stress, while the AGI and Aragonite indices decrease with stress.

In addition, the single stressor indices are generated at full 3d depth, but to combine them into the MSI, we reduce it to a 2D which includes a measure of the habitable depth range for each species as shown in table 1. For the fishes, we include species depth range by taking the average over their entire habitable depth range. For corals, seaweed and mussels, as they inhabit the sea floor exclusively, we take the deepest wet point in the water column.

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In the following we describe the normalisation process for each of the single stressors that are integrated in the multi-stressor index.

AGI

The AGI normalisation process is straightforward. The AGI_{crit} is a pre-defined threshold which is calculated using the same input data as the other AGI parameters. Stress starts to occur when $AGI < AGI_{crit}$. The normalisation equation below inverts the scale of the AGI, such that all AGI values above AGI_{crit} have a zero AGI_{norm} (i.e., no stress), but the AGI_{norm} tends to 1 as values of AGI below AGI_{crit} tend to zero (i.e., very stressed).

$$AGI_{norm} = 1 - \frac{AGI}{AGI_{crit}}$$

HWHI

The HWHI normalisation is straightforward. Each species' sensitivity to heat waves is already included in the HWHI calculation through the historical temperature range of their habitat. The HWHI is then normalised with a simple scaling factor, $HWHI_{scaling}$. In the equation below:

$$HWHI_{norm} = \frac{HWHI}{HWHI_{scaling}}$$

Where $HWHI_{scaling} = 100$. This value is set such that a HWHI value of 100 or more is normalised to 1. The HWHI is the total number of days higher than the temperature threshold multiplied by the difference between the temperature and the temperature threshold. This means that we define "very stressed" as approximately one month per year at 3 degrees warmer than the species' habitat's 95th percentile temperature – although this could equally be interpreted as 3 months at one degree warmer than the threshold. By definition, a short intense heat wave may result in the same HWHI as a longer but less intense heat wave. Further tuning of the scaling factor may be required at a later stage.

Aragonite Saturation

The Aragonite saturation index indicates a very stressed environment when Aragonite saturation is below 1, and stressed when Aragonite saturation is below 3, and no stress above 3. However, this is only for marine calcifiers (organisms with calcium carbonate structures such as corals and molluscs). Fishes and seaweed are likely to be insensitive to acidification. The following normalisation equation considers each species' sensitivity to Aragonite, but also inverts the scale so that it is in line with our MSI normalisation:

$$Arag_{norm} = 1 - \frac{Arag}{Arag_{scaling}}$$

Table 8 shows the sensitivity of each species and the scaling factor, $Arag_{scaling}$, that we applied in the normalisation.

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Table 8: 5 Aragonite Saturation scaling factors.

Species	Sensitivity	Aragonite scaling factor
Fishes (Cod, Herring, Seabass & Seabream)	Not sensitive	1.25
Blue Mussels	Sensitive	3
Cold Water Corals	Very sensitive	4
Seaweeds	Sensitive	3

Hypoxia

We've defined the hypoxia index as the cumulative sum of every time that the daily oxygen concentration falls below 180umol/Kg for at least three days. As such, we can estimate that a scaling factor of 1000 is equivalent to a high-stress anoxic event of 10 consecutive days below 80 umol/kg.

To include hypoxia in the MSI, we needed to understand each species' relationship with hypoxia. We then generated hypoxia scaling values to normalize the hypoxia index for each species. We applied the following normalisation equation:

$$Hypox_{norm} = \frac{Hypox}{Hypox_{scaling}}$$

We used the following hypoxia index scaling factors for the normalisation process.

Table 9: 6 Hypoxia Index Scaling Factors.

Species	Sensitivity	Hypoxia scaling factor (Larger means more resilient)
Atlantic Herring - <i>Clupea harengus</i>	Sensitive	500
Atlantic Cod - <i>Gadus morhua</i>	Sensitive	500
Seabass - <i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	Sensitive	500
Seabream - <i>Sparus aurata</i>	Sensitive	500
Blue Mussels - <i>Mytilus edulis</i>	Resilient	1000
Cold Water Corals	Very resilient	1500
Seaweeds	Very resilient	1500

The Hypoxia index has units of mmol O₂ * days m⁻³. This means that a hypoxia index of 1000 can be interpreted as, for instance, 100 days of slightly hypoxic water (170 mmol O₂ m⁻³) or 10 days of very hypoxic water (80 mmol O₂ m⁻³) per year, with at least three consecutive days below the threshold. For resilient species, we set the hypoxia scaling value of 1000, such that hypoxia indices greater than 1000 indicate high stress for resilient organisms. We set a scaling factor of 500 for sensitive organisms and a scaling factor of 1500 for very resilient organisms. Note that these values are approximations based on limited evidence and future iterations of the MSI may want to perform additional tuning of this parameter.

In fish species, Hypoxia can impact swimming performance, decreasing speed, impacting predator-prey interactions, reducing school density and changing schooling behaviours. However, fish can avoid

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hypoxia and travel to well-oxygenated areas. As such, hypoxia can impact species distributions. In aquaculture, where fish are limited to their sea cages, the effects of hypoxia may be particularly damaging (Domenici & Herbert, 2013). Both Seabass and Seabream are sensitive to hypoxia (Samaras et al., 2023). Laboratory induced hypoxia reduced Atlantic Cod food consumption and growth rates (Chabot & Dutil, 1999), but wild cod are able to move to less hypoxic regions. Blue Mussels are resilient to short term hypoxic and anoxic events but have lower spawning rates under prolonged (2 weeks) hypoxia (Kong & Sokolova, 2025). While there is evidence that tropical coral reefs are vulnerable to hypoxia, cold water corals, have been shown to be resilient (Hebbeln et al., 2020). Seaweed are likely to be very resilient to hypoxia, as they occur only in shallow well-mixed waters, are able to photosynthesis, and their grazers are likely to be more sensitive to hypoxia (Ng & Micheli, 2020)(Ng & Micheli, 2020).

Plastic Exposure Stressor Index

The Plastic exposure stressor index is an exposure map showing the collocation of high plastic concentrations with high concentration of marine life in the NWS and Arctic regions. These spatial maps will be normalized using a two-factor process. Initially, by dividing all values by the maximum of the entire domain, to result in a range of values between [0,1]. The plastic exposure stressor then needs to be further scaled to be roughly in line with the harm induced by the other indices. For instance, some fish, seaweed or coral will die in a high stress heat wave or hypoxia at the normalised stress value of 1. However, a plastic exposure value of 1 is likely to be non-fatal, so it needs to be scaled downwards such that it is comparable with the other indices in the multi-stressor index.

$$E'(x, y) = F_{plastic} * \frac{E(x, y)}{\max(E(x, y))}$$

Where:

- $E'(x,y)$ is the normalised plastic exposure index,
- $E(x,y)$ is the exposure at position (x,y),
- $F_{plastic}$ is the scaling factor.

The scaling factor will need to be tuned when data becomes available, but we will initially start simply with a multiplying factor of $F_{plastic} = \frac{1}{4}$. It is possible that it is too early to try to build risk indices for exposure to plastics, as simply there is not enough evidence and knowledge about possible effects of exposure to plastic and consequences to species. In addition, there is probably a significant time lag between exposure and effect.

Oil spill hazard index

The oil spill hazard index already ranges from 0-1, but in practice, it tends to be very close to zero with its largest values in this model approximately $1e-2$. This means that it may depress the mean of the other values. The existing model simulations for this index were performed in the Mediterranean so we cannot include the oil spill index in the multi-stressor index for the NWS. Additional tuning may be needed for oil spill indices to be included in the MSI, in order to bring it up to similar scaling as the other indices. For instance, by dividing the index by some factor of the typical regional maximum.

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Ecotoxicological studies are inherently limited by the exposure time of the experiments, which cannot cover a lifetime of chronic exposure as in the field. Therefore, exposure concentrations are often higher than those in the field, and the risk quotient is usually lower than 1. If a value above 1 occurs, it is reset to 1 as it represents a high (maximum) risk.

POPs Normalisation

Ecological risk assessments for PCB 153 in fish tissue commonly use a 10 ng/g wet weight safety threshold, ww_{thresh} . As such, we suggest this factor as to scale the PCB concentration into an index with a range of 0 to 1.

$$PCBI = \frac{PCB_{conc}}{ww_{thresh}}$$

When PCBI is greater than 1, the index indicates a high stress regime. The modelled data show an average concentration of 2.6 ng/g wet weight, yielding a risk index of roughly 0.3. These results indicate current PCB 153 levels are substantially below the safety threshold, suggesting minimal ecological risk to aquatic systems.

Fishing Pressure Index

The fishing pressure index (FPI) is initially scaled such that 0 indicates a high fishing stress and 1 indicates low stress. This is the opposite of the other MSI values 0 (low stress) to 1 (high stress). To normalise these values such that they can be included in the MSI, we apply the following basic scaling function:

$$FPI = 1 - 1 * \frac{FPI}{FPI_{scaling}}$$

Where the Fishing Pressure Index Scaling, $FPI_{scaling}$, is initially set to a value of 1, but can be tuned in the future as needed. It is likely that fishing pressure will be the dominant source of stress in the MSI for commercially significant species. In those cases, $FPI_{scaling}$ should be set to a value greater than one.

Methodology to validate the reliability of the CC indices

The evaluation procedures recommended by the CMEMS product quality working group will be adopted to validate the reliability of the CC indices (Mercator Ocean, 2022). The validation of the NECCTON model's physical processes, marine biogeochemistry, ecosystems will be performed elsewhere in the project but is an important part of the validation process.

Once the modelled environment has been shown to have a demonstrable quality, we can safely use the data outputs. Our proposed validation and tuning process is:

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1. First validate the physical environment, including the Temperature, Salinity, Mixed Layer Depth, and ocean circulation patterns of the model against contemporary historical observations.
2. Secondly, validate the marine biogeochemistry, including surface chlorophyll, nutrient concentrations, pH, oxygen concentrations against contemporary historical observations and data products.
3. Generate each of the CC stressor indices, and check that they are behaving sensibly in the known habitats of the species. Then generate the pollutant stressor indices and verify that they line up with known historical behaviour.
4. Compare the modelled stressor index against the indices calculated using historical observations. Tune each index to be more compatible with the historical version of index.
5. Tune the individual stressor normalisation MSI such that the known habitat in the historical period lines up with areas of relatively low stress.

In all cases, input datasets need to be treated cautiously such that we are not validate the indices against the data that was used to parameterise them, especially the species habitat data.

6. Results

In this section, we show several of the indices that were tested using sample data from the Resolving Climate Impacts on shelf and Coastal sea Ecosystems (ReCICLE) project simulations. The overall aim of this project was to identify and quantify the potential future response to climate change of the simple plant life (phytoplankton) forming the base of the food chain of the shelf sea ecosystems and to assess the likely range of this response using a state of the art coupled hydrodynamic-ecosystem model at an exceptionally fine resolution. As such, ReCICLE model simulations are an excellent starting point for testing the climate change stressors. These results are for the sample model simulation and will be recalculated using the NECCTON model outputs. The NECCTON outputs for the marine pollution and stressor products are planned to be validated and released by month 36 of the project. (MS8.3).

Single Climate Change Stressor performances

This work package includes 16 single climate change stressor indices. The following sets of figures show groups of these indices, in their native units, for the year 1990.

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Figure 6. Single species AGI for the year 1990, in the surface ocean.

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Figure 7. Single species HWHI, for the year 1990, in the surface.

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The Aerobic Growth Index in figure 6 is unitless, and scales inversely such that lower values indicate more stressed – indicated by the darker regions on the maps. However, the scaling is relative to the critical AGI value, there is no stress when the AGI is above the critical AGI value. This makes it challenging to directly interpret the AGI in their pre-normalised state. The normalised AGI values are shown in the MSI section below.

The HWHI is shown in figure 7. As opposed to the AGI, the HWHI, scales such that higher values indicate higher stress. In these figures, the lighter colours indicate heat stress. The HWHI was tuned using the species-specific habitat, so the scaling on figures should be comparable. In year 1990, there should be relatively little stress for the heat tolerant species. Note that the [unitless] units given in D8.1 Table 3.6.6 is incorrect, as the units for HWHI are degree C*days. The seaweed HWHI temperature threshold is particularly low, at 13.3 degree C.

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Figure 8. Aragonite Saturation index and Hypoxia Index. The dots in the Aragonite saturation represent the regions where the surface falls below a value of 3, which is a level considered stressful for calcifiers.

Figure 8 shows Aragonite Saturation index and Hypoxia Index. Aragonite saturation index is typically highest at the sea surface, with large parts of the region having a saturation index below 3. This lines up with expected values (Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2017). There are very few calcifiers like corals or mussels living at the sea surface, and the other species are insensitive to aragonite saturation.

The Hypoxia index in Figure 8 is the integral hypoxia index in the z-direction, which shows the full volume of hypoxic events over the domain. Most of the domain has no hypoxia in 1990, but a few small pockets exist in the Bay of Biscay, Skagerrak straight, and west of Ireland and Scottish in their near-coastal waters. This is expected behaviour for the NWS, as existing studies have shown that even the seabed oxygen concentration in these regions rarely drops below 6 mg/l (Wakelin et al., 2020). The units for the Hypoxia index are $\text{mmol O}_2 \text{ m}^{-3} \cdot \text{days}$, and the [unitless] units given in D8.1 Table 3.6.6 are incorrect. It is only after the species-specific normalisation process that the hypoxia index becomes unitless.

Single stressor normalisation

The normalisation process converts from the indices' native units to a standardized scale where 0 is not stressed and 1 is very stressed. However, the scaling factor and normalisation decisions means that a subjective judgement was often needed to finalise the scaling. While we've made effort to back up the normalisation process with observational evidence, there may be some implicit biases which are hard to isolate and correct. In practice, there is no objective way to combine stressors as we often don't know the full impact of the stressor directly on each species. Examples of the normalised individual stressors built from the four CC indices (AGI, HWHI, Hypoxia and Aragonite saturation) are shown below in the next section in figures 9-15. Future iterations of this work will include contributions from the other indices (oil spill index, Mercury, POPs, Plastics and fishing pressure).

Multi-Stressor indices Comparison of historical and future indices

In the figures below, we compare the individual and multi-stressor indices calculated for year 1995 against the year 2095 in the NWS domain for each species. This aims to be a demonstration of the kind of insight that we may be able to achieve with the final datasets. We do not intend for these figures to be shown externally, or in a scientific context. By comparing two years separated by a century, we can see the extreme and broad scale impacts of severe climate change.

Each of these figures show the normalised indices in the top two rows, the observed habitats in the bottom left and the MSI in the bottom right. The left figure shows the modelled year 1995 and the right-hand figure is the RCP8.5 modelled year 2095. In all figures, the normalised hypoxia index is very low over most of the domain, as the NWS is not a region where we expect to see high hypoxic coverage.

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Figure 9. 1995 vs 2095: Atlantic Herring

Atlantic herring, shown in Figure 9, are more significantly impacted by the warming in the southern regions of their historical range. The HWHI stressor is likely over-tuned as several regions that have an $HWHI_{norm}$ near 1 in the historical period form part of the herring’s native habitat. The Aragonite saturation index rises to be a low source of stress over much of the domain, but there is little overlap between those regions and the herring’s historical habitat. In addition, herring are insensitive to acidification.

Figure 10. 1995 vs 2095: Cold Water Coral

Cold Water coral, shown in figure 10, are sensitive to acidification, seen here via Aragonite saturation. Though changes in AGI may also impact them, in the Southwest region of the domain, but they have not previously been observed there in large numbers – though the observational datasets of the

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seafloor may be patchy in this region. While they are likely to be sensitive to heat waves, extreme heat waves are less likely at the depths that cold water corals may inhabit on the seafloor in this domain. It is possible that the 100 degree*day 5-day threshold is an inappropriate selection criterion for the off-shelf seafloor. It is possible that small but enduring changes in Seafloor temperature may be equally stressful as short-term heat waves for cold water coral and other species.

Figure 11. 1995 vs 2095: Seabass

Seabass, shown in figure 11, are relatively resilient to the stressors included here across this domain. They have a high thermal and aragonite tolerance, the index that has the largest change, the aragonite saturation, is mostly outside their historical habitat. It is likely that the largest influence on their future habitat will be fishing pressure, which is not included in this figure.

Figure 12. 1995 vs 2095: Atlantic Cod

Atlantic Cod, shown in figure 12, historically lived towards the northern part of the North Sea domain and similar latitudes. The Heat stress in the Southern North Sea and in the coastal area in this historical period is due to the historically low presence in these regions: the HWI tuning was performed using this habitat map, so there are not statistically independent! In the future, this high stress region will grow in a northward direction and the Cod will likely become stressed if they remain in the southern

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part of their historical habitat. We also expect a northward migration as the southern parts of this domain become increasingly inhospitable. We do not see significant changes in AGI, hypoxia or Aragonite saturation.

Figure 13. 1995 vs 2095: Blue Mussels

Blue Mussels are shown in figure 13. In the historical period, large parts of the NWS domain appear to be a high stress habitat for blue mussels. The blue mussels are not observed in these regions, so the parameterisation process may accurately capture the habitat as a stressor. The bulk of this stress originates from the AGI_{norm} value, but it's not clear that this index is suitable for deployment on mussels. In the future, Blue mussels may be impacted by changes in HWHI in southern North Sea, but also by changes in aragonite saturation elsewhere in the domain.

Figure 14. 1995 vs 2095: Seaweeds

The seaweeds MSI in figure 14 has significant regions of AGI, HWHI and aragonite saturation stressors. Most of these high stress regions occur in places that seaweeds are unlikely to inhabit, mostly due to the seafloor depth being too great. However, the southern North Sea is a region of high HWHI stress even in the historical period. Using the same method as the other species, we found that the T_{Thres} for

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seaweed was 13 degrees, which seems inappropriately low. In comparison to the future, where AGI, HWHI and Aragonite all contribute to stress across the domain.

Figure 15. 1995 vs 2095: Seabream

Seabream, shown in figure 15, are resistant to the projected changes in these indices, and both the historical and future period show very little stress in these four indices. The largest change occurs in the Aragonite saturation index, which is largely outside their historical habitat range, and they are known to have relatively low susceptibility to acidification.

Evaluating the indices in other MFCs model

It is expected to be straightforward to extend these tools to applications in the other NEMO-ERSEM domains. To calculate these four indices, the input data requirements include:

- Daily 3D Temperature
- Daily 3D Oxygen
- Monthly 3D Aragonite Saturation. This is typically produced by ERSEM at runtime but can be calculated instead using the method describe above, which requires monthly mean 3D Temperature, Salinity, Pressure and Carbonate ion concentration fields.

The input parameters for this analysis are contained within a single yaml file, so generating a second version of that file may be enough to migrate this analysis to a second domain. The species-specific parameterisations for AGI and HWHI were calculated using the global distributions of species habitats, so they are likely to be representative for these species in other domains. However, it is possible that even if the habitat is suitable, the species in question is not endemic to the region. In all cases, the individual species need to be validated against observational evidence.

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7. Conclusion

Summary

We developed tools for mapping integrated climate change stressors in four new indices: Aerobic Growth Index, Aragonite Saturation index, Hypoxia index, and Heat Wave Hazard index, and for four pollutant indices: oil spills, POPs, plastics and Mercury. We explained the calculation of the indices, then applied the CC indices to a small subset of sample data from existing models in the Northwest European Shelf. We normalised the indices to a common scale, then combined them into a multi-stressor index, and demonstrated a use case by identifying several changes in stress in the NWS over the coming century. We also show recent progress in the development of several other indices: the oil spill index, mercury concentration, the persistent organic pollutant PCB 135, fishing pressure and plastic.

Limitations and Extensions

The AGI is designed to quantify species specific impacts of habitat variability. It is designed to study individual species of motile vertebrates, not sessile invertebrates like Blue Mussels, or wider groups like “Cold-water coral” or “seaweed”. In private correspondence, the authors of Morée et al. (2023) communicated that AGI may not produce sensible output for Blue Mussels, Seaweeds, or Cold-water corals. So, while it is technically possible to apply these methods to these groups, it may not be sensible or straightforward to interpret. Further studies are needed to understand how this AGI should be interpreted for mussels, corals and seaweeds, or whether some other index would be more appropriate. For instance, instead of looking at aggregate groups, individual species of Cold-Water Coral and seaweed may be studied for the AGI or HWHI methods to be applied.

The AGI includes input data from both temperature and dissolved oxygen concentration, so by including the AGI, Hypoxia index and HWHI, we may be double counting these impacts in the MSI. A statistical analysis of the independence of AGI, HWHI Hypoxia would inform whether they all need to be included in MSI, or whether they should be included with reduced weighting.

The HWHI uses a species-specific warming threshold and does not consider climatological or seasonal effects. For instance, in addition to summer heat waves where the warmest part of the year becomes hotter, some species may also be vulnerable to excess warming at other times in their life cycle, for instance in the cooler winter months, which is unlikely to be captured in the HWHI. A more complex HWHI index which incorporates annual climatology could be developed to take into account for these changes.

The AGI and HWHI tunings were performed with annual WOA data, so the response is only representative of the mean annual behaviour. A higher time resolution temperature dataset, ideally daily, would be needed to understand historical habitat. However, daily temperature may not exist for the time period in question, and high temporal habitat data is unlikely to exist at all for any of these species. In addition, the WOA data used to determine the AGI and HWHI parameters has a resolution

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of 1°x1°, which is relatively coarse and may not be sufficient to capture local scale temperature, salinity and oxygen variability.

The habitat datasets that we used from fishbase.se may be not representative of the real habitat. In addition, by combining several decades of presence/absence data, we may mask changes in the habitat over that time period. In addition, several of the habitats were sparsely populated, for instance the seaweed and cold-water corals, which becomes more of a problem when using coarse scale annual temperature datasets.

These indices are unlikely to cover the entire set of challenges faced by these species and groups of organisms. For instance, there is nothing about increased storminess – which may have significant impacts on seaweeds. In addition, there are non-climate change related sources of stress which may prevent species from inhabiting a region: for instance, the water column may be too deep, or contain insufficient food sources, or competition from other species, or too much predation, or temperatures too low, etc. Finally, fishing is one of the largest drivers of changing fish populations, but not currently included as a pressure in the MSI. One additional refinement could include only indices which are relevant on a species-specific basis, taking into account other pressures and excluding indices that are non-relevant.

The software input would benefit from additional refinement. The MSI generation is currently run from a single yml file. This makes it more challenging to include the other non-Climate change indices into the MSI analysis. In future revisions, we would recommend splitting the generation of individual indices from the MSI generation into two separate executables.

Several of the normalisation values were estimated based on expert knowledge, and additional tuning may be required. For instance, the HWHI scaling factor of 100 is used for all species, but it's possible that a different value here would be more effective, or that different species are more sensitive to warming above their temperature threshold. The MSI method aims to be a useful indicator of stress on organisms but may be sensitive to the total number of stressors added. For instance, right now the MSI includes 4 stressors. When we add the oil spill index, the MSI will be lower, as the oil spill stressor value is typically close to zero in most places. This means that the two different MSIs that have different input stressors are not directly comparable.

The original questionnaire that was used to determine species selection included the following question:

Can you suggest some relevant species, not necessarily directly exploited, but important from an ecological perspective (e.g. **habitat forming seagrass**, charismatic species like **cold water corals**, etc.)

By listing these two species as examples, this is a leading question that primes the respondents by providing suggested answers. The respondents are more likely to suggest the exemplified species in their responses, independently of how useful, important or feasible it would be to include these species.

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The seaweed habitat is almost entirely coastal, but we are using a coarse resolution World Ocean Atlas (WOA) temperature dataset as input to calculate the AGI and HWHI parameters. This may be adding a cold bias. In effect, both the seafloor depth and bottom water temperature will likely be lower in a coarse 100km x 100km grid cell than in a shallow coastal site. This effect is true for all species, but it likely to be particularly impactful for seaweed as they live in shallow coastal waters. The seaweed temperature threshold was calculated to be 13.3 °C, which seems too low, given their coastal shallow habitat. Our seaweed class includes a wide diversity of species that each has its own habitat, temperature range, and life cycle. Future iterations of this work could instead focus on a smaller number of commercially or ecologically valuable species, and a higher resolution temperature dataset to more accurately capture their sensitivity to heat.

Cold water coral occurs only in deep water and off the shelf. However, this model domain was designed to simulate the shelf, and it's unlikely that it will accurately capture changes in deep waters. In the global modelling context, CMIP models takes millennia to spin up deep ocean carbon cycle, which was not done here. As such, it's unlikely that any NWS model will accurately capture the deep ocean carbon cycle. In addition, cold water coral input data is particularly sparse, there is little literature describing them, their habitat in the deep ocean sees smaller changes than the surface oceans, and they are not a known important fishery. While they are scientifically interesting, ecologically important and charismatic, a more robust case needs to be built before we can recommend including them as a valuable species in future iterations here.

The sample model data used in this report uses atmospheric forcing from the RCP8.5 scenario in its simulation. The RCP 8.5 forcing dates from CMIP5 simulations, where the historical models ran until 2005, and the first year of the “future simulations” was 2006. This means that this simulation has no information about any of the historical warming or emissions since 2006, and it also misses several of the generation model improvements and bias reductions from CMIP6. This data is simply a sample to demonstrate the methodology, and figures from this deliverable should not be used to make policy decisions.

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